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Review Article

**PROMISING THERAPEUTIC DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS
FOR GLAUCOMA: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW****¹Dr Ifrah Fatima Zafar, ²Dr Lubna Asgher, ³Dr Muhammad Ahmad.**¹MBBS, Ameer Ud Din Medical College, Lahore.²MBBS, Fatima Memorial Hospital and Medical College, Lahore.³MBBS, Hamdard Medical and Dental College, Karachi.**Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

The aim of this review is basically to analyze the new different drug delivery therapy that is currently administered to patients on different stages of development across the globe.

Ocular inserts is a therapeutic drug intervention in which micro devices around the eye impregnated formed of sterile drug and release the drugs for a longer duration. These inserts are categorized into insoluble, soluble and bio-erodible on the basis of their physical and chemical properties. Due to reduced washout by tears the bioavailability of the drug increases by manifold and the inserts increases the ocular surface contact time of the drug to a few days.

The most significant advantage of these devices will be the improvement in the quality of life of the patients who currently have to adhere to a strict regime of repeatedly putting eye drops throughout the day.

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INTRODUCTION:

The second most common cause of blindness in the world is glaucoma. Visual field loss usually observed in patients who are presented with glaucoma and having raised intra ocular pressure which results in optic neuropathy. Approximately 60 million people around the globe have optic neuropathy secondary to glaucoma. Literature has stated that in the initial 20 years of the first glaucomatous changes there is primary angle glaucoma which leads to bilateral blindness in 9% and unilateral blindness in 27% patients. There was an estimation of 4.5 and 3.9 million people in 2010 those were diagnosed with bilateral blindness cause of open angle glaucoma and angle closure glaucoma respectively. But this ratio is supposed to be 5.9 and 5.3 million of bilaterally blind people due to OAF and ACG in 2012 respectively. The visual field loss which occurs due to glaucoma is an irreversible and progressive. But this progression of visual field loss can be alleviated by targeting the intra ocular pressure within the normal range. Patient presenting with diagnosed OAG can be managed by anti-glaucoma drugs whereas lowering the IOP is the first step in the management strategy for high risk glaucoma. The successfully slowing down the progression of vision and visual field loss totally depends upon the timely diagnosis and availability of prescribed drugs. And if administering drugs the outcome depends upon the prescribed amount if drug to ocular tissue, should not interfere with normal functioning of eye and easy to administer. The aim of managing ocular hypertension and promoting neuro-protection an important compliance is needed among the patients and to prevent blindness. The aim of this review is basically to analyze the new different drug delivery therapy that is currently administered to patients on different stages of development across the globe.

Ocular inserts

Ocular inserts is a therapeutic drug intervention in which micro devices around the eye impregnated formed of sterile drug and release the drugs for a longer duration. These inserts are categorized into insoluble, soluble and bio-erodible on the basis of their physical and chemical properties. Due to reduced washout by tears the bioavailability of the drug increases by manifold and the inserts increases the ocular surface contact time of the drug to a few days. A study conducted by Maichuk has first reported about the drug administration through inferior clu-de-sac. When the drug is inserted it converts into a viscous polymer and softens after initial 10-15s contact with the tear and conversion into a polymer solution occurs within 60-90 min of administration. Complete dissolving takes up to an

hour however this steady solution releases the drug. An immediate change in this consistency of SODI occurs after its insertion into conjunctival sac.

Ocusert

The earliest models of ocular inserts were developed by Armaly and Rao. The ocular insert has the ability to release drug up to extended period for 7 days with constant rate of 20 or 40 ug per hour. It requires weekly replacement and inserted in the upper or lower cul-de-sac. From the ocusert pilocarpine releases and it specifically target organs in the iris, ciliary body, and trabecular meshwork. A study has compared the results of convention eye drops of pilocarpine and pilocarpine loaded ocusert. It was noted that insertion with pilocarpine has greater effect of reduction as compared to conventional eye drops. Another study conducted by Zimmerman and his colleagues has conducted pilocarpine ocusert in 40 patients with specific release rate of 20 µg/h. 25.6±5.6 mmHg was recorded the initial mean of intra ocular pressure (IOP). Whereas after administration of pilocarpine loaded ocusert, the IOP was came to 19.9±3.9 mmHg. It has further stated that patient's preference was also ocusert therapy over the pilocarpine drops. There was no side effect observed from the Ocusert therapy. Another study has given the statistics of achieving good control of IOP by releasing 20 or 40 ug per hour with pilocarpine loaded ocusert therapy. The observed side effects were very minimum or almost none. Ocusert could not become widely accepted on the basis of clinical studies which have shown positive outcomes. Although many patients had not given satisfactory feedback in controlling IOP because they have faced many difficulties regarding device insertion such as irritation, drug insertion and ejection of the device from the eye.

Ocufit SR

Escalon Ophthalmics was the first to develop ocufit SR. It is made up of flexible rod-shaped silicon elastomer device which has designed for controlled release of drugs over long periods in conjunctival fornix for retention. Different models are available with length which varies maximum between 25 and 30 mm whereas having 1.9mm in diameter. Study conducted by Katz and Blackman has reported that there was minimum expulsion of rod-shaped device as compared to oval and flat inserts. Sustained and long retention drug release is the property of insoluble ocufit. In 70% of the participant the placebo device was more sustained up to 2 weeks when placed in the upper fornix.

Minidisc

The minidisc or ocular therapeutic system was developed by bawa and colleagues. A contact lens having a diameter of 4-5mm with concave and convex faces and latter it substantially conforms to the sclera of the eye. This minidisc has formed by hydroxyethyl methacrylate and ethylene glycol methacrylate. This contact lens has easy placement of the device without any foreign body sensation, distortion in vision or decreased oxygen permeability and can be fit in upper or lower lid.

New Ophthalmic Delivery System

A water-soluble film loaded used to place drug in the lower conjunctival sac this is called new ophthalmic delivery system which is used for delivering drugs in precise amount to the eye. Water soluble polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) have used in the manufacturing of NODS. A study conducted by Greaves and colleagues, they used radiolabeled NOS which was loaded with pilocarpine nitrate. They analyzed the bioavailability and pharmacokinetic in the human subject. They have showed an eightfold precorneal bioavailability and higher compliance among the test subjects pilocarpine NODS as compared with a 2% w/v pilocarpine nitrate solution.

Therapeutic contact lenses

An ideal drug delivery system was found availability and easy application of contact lens. In comparison with eye drop formulations, contact lenses have 50% more bioavailability and having a favorable property of extended wear. It has help in better sustaining and regulated ocular drug delivery. Soft contact lenses are water-soluble polymeric hydrogels, cross-linked to form networks. These hydrogel lenses are widely used for drug delivery, even though the delivery of water-soluble drugs, such as timolol and dorzolamide, elutes from the highly hydrated polymer networks rapidly. In comparison, the soft contact lenses manufactured by polymerization N,N-diethyl acrylamide and methacrylic acid deliver timolol over a prolonged period.

Soak and release

By using fluorescein stain as drug delivery, Waltman and Kaufman was the first to develop the potential use of hydrophilic polymers of 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA). Through soft contact lenses, antiglaucoma drugs have been administered by Hillman in 1974. For drug delivery he used polymers of vinyl pyrrolidone soaked in 1% pilocarpine. He has reported the therapeutic effects to be as efficacious as 4% pilocarpine topical eye drops.

Microemulsion-loaded lenses

The most favored drug dispersal was microemulsions because of their favorable properties such as high drug-loading capacity, thermodynamic stability, and ease of preparation, increased wettability, and easy tailoring of drug release pattern. Various companies have manufactured drug-loaded microemulsion-incorporating contact lenses. The researcher has used silica shell using octadecyltrimethoxysilane (OTMS) with encapsulated timolo in microemulsion followed by dispersion in hydrogel lens. It has shown positive results of up to eight days without influencing the transparency of the lens. Another study conducted by Li and colleagues they demonstrated contact lenses loaded with timolol, with oil-in-water-type microemulsions using a combination of ethyl butyrate and Pluronic F127. This timolo microemulsion- loaded gels model has revealed that there is slow and extended period of drug release in DI water. Due to long-term degradation of the gel delivery rates showed a sigmoidal shape. It can be used as a vehicle for hydrophobic drug delivery to the ocular surface because the systems have very high timolo loading.

Vitamin E-loaded lenses

An in situ transport barrier for timolo was designated by Chauhan and colleagues by using Vitamin E. The loading concentration of vitamin E was elevated from 10% to 40% in contact lenses so the drug release was significantly increased. By using vitamin E loading the group has exhibit that there was quadratic increase in the drug release. Loadings of 10% and 40% Vitamin E increased the release time of timolol by a factor of about 5 and 400, respectively. This loading of vitamin E has some negative influence such as an increase in lens sizes, a reduction in oxygen diffusion, and a significant reduction in ion permeability.

Enzyme-triggered timolol release

Timolo loaded nanodiamonds contact lens was demonstrated by Kim and colleagues. It acts as an enzyme trigger for the delivery of timolo from the ND-nanogel embedded contact lens. The nanogels sequester timolol prior activation of the lysozyme that causes chitosan degradation and subsequently allow sustained drug release. The total steady release from the lens was 9.41µg after 24-h of treatment with lysozyme. But after 48 hours of lysozyme treatment there was some variability was seen in the drug release. Some of the factors were maintained at practical levels such as optical clarity, water content, and oxygen permeability. The decreased ion and oxygen permeability, protein adherence, alterations in mechanical properties, and lens-related infections due

to continuous wear significantly limit the application of contact lenses for drug delivery.

Subconjunctival inserts

As a replacement for viscoelastic depot delivery injections the subconjunctival inserts are used as implants. It was exhibited by ViSci Inc in 2014 a VS101 ocular insert. It is still under research process in multicenter to evaluate the safety and effectiveness of subconjunctival latanoprost insert in subjects with ocular hypertension or OAG.

PCL-PEG inserts

Ng and colleagues used a biodegradable microfilm synthesized by a combination of poly(lactide)/poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PLC) and poly(ϵ -caprolactone)/poly(ethylene glycol) (PLC/PCL-PEG). The polymer was loaded with timolol maleate and inserted by conjunctival dissection.³⁹ The authors reported a reduction of $50.1\% \pm 8.5\%$ in IOP from baseline in primates with ocular hypertension, which was sustained for 140 days.

AP-PCL inserts

Alkoxyphenacyl-based polycarbonate copolymers in combination with polycaprolactone (AP-PCL) were used by Manickavasagam and colleagues for sustained delivery of brimonidine tartrate for up to 3 months. The major drawback attributed to the subconjunctival inserts is the requirement of a surgically invasive procedure, which creates a small opening in the conjunctiva with a possibility of subconjunctival migration, infection, and need of an Operating Room procedure for insertion and removal of the device.

Microneedles

A manufacturing of device by using metals or polymers with dimension with the diameter ranged between 10 and 200 μ m is called microneedle. This manufacturing has made it less invasive and more targeted to the sites of drug action. Some researchers have used stainless steel microneedles with exceeding the diameter up to 500- to 750- μ m and deliver it to pilocarpine into the anterior chamber via the intrascleral route. They have demonstrated that by using this model the drug absorption has elevated to 45-fold as compared with conventional eye drops.

Discussion:

Literature has emphasized on the proper management of glaucoma with importance of adherence, compliance, and persistence. However the available therapeutic drugs are successful in lowering the IOP and doing the neuro-protection but the new methods of topical delivery have seem to be inefficient due to

poor target bioavailability, increased systemic absorption, and poor patient compliance. Many new devices have been reviewed in this article but they are in initial stages of their development and not available in market. The impact of these devices can be evaluated once they are available in clinical use and extensive data is available to evaluate their efficacy. The glaucoma management of these new devices is further needed to be emphasized but at present there is lack of data. In the geriatric and pediatric group eye drop administration is a difficult process. By minimizing the drug wastage effective localized delivery will prevent drug loss due to systemic absorption and first-pass metabolism. The high prevalence of ocular surface disease in patients instilling antiglaucoma drugs with added preservatives may be overcome with the newer devices. The most significant advantage of these devices will be the improvement in the quality of life of the patients who currently have to adhere to a strict regime of repeatedly putting eye drops throughout the day

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